

DEVELOPMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF MATURE COCONUT (*COCOS NUCIFERA L.*) WATER AS AN ALTERNATIVE FOR DISTILLED WATER IN REAGENT PREPARATION FOR BASIC SOAP MAKING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Coconut (*Cocos nucifera L.*), a member of the *Arecaceae* family, is cultivated in tropical regions. Humans have utilized its structures, with the fruit being valuable, producing food and non-food products. Its global market demand remains high, valued at USD 11.5 billion and projected to reach USD 31.1 billion by 2026. This study focuses on the development and assessment of the mature coconut water as an alternative for distilled water in soap-making process. The physicochemical properties of the soap produced, including pH, moisture content, and foam height, were compared with those of a commercial soap. Soap samples were prepared using standardized procedures, with mature coconut water replacing distilled water in the saponification reaction. Results indicated that the soap made with coconut water had a higher pH (10.30 ± 0.06), higher moisture content ($16.02 \pm 0.10\%$), and lower foam height ($1.57 \pm 0.06\text{cm}$) compared to the commercial soap. Statistical analysis using t-test revealed significant differences in all measured parameters ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that the coconut water influenced the soap's characteristics. The findings demonstrate that mature coconut water can serve as an alternative aqueous medium in soap production, producing a cleansing soap with acceptable physicochemical properties. This substitution offers a sustainable approach to utilizing coconut resources while maintaining soap quality.

Keywords: *Coconut, Coconut water, Soap, Soap-making, Sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

Coconut (*Cocos nucifera L.*) is a fruit that grows in the coconut tree. It is a monocot that belongs to the family Arecaceae, subfamily Cocoideae and is the sole species of the genus *Cocos*. Tall and dwarf are the only significant categories of coconut in the world (Gurbuz & Manaros, 2019). However, due to natural and artificial selection, additional varietal groups had been created: typical, nana, and hybrids. Both immature (green) and mature (brown and dry) coconut have exocarp which is impermeable and the mesocarp is made up of dense fiber which make the coconut to be buoyant. In addition, both mature and immature fruit contains coconut water which are very rich in electrolytes (Ignacio & Miguel, 2021).

The Philippines has approximately 20 million hectares of land suitable for coconut cultivation, with varying levels of suitability. However, based on 2021 PSA data, only 3.64 million hectares, or 18% of these suitable areas, are currently planted with coconuts (Francisco et al., 2024). Out of the country's 81 provinces, 68 are involved in coconut farming (Sagena, 2020). The coconut meets nearly all of humanity's basic needs, providing food, shelter, medicine, fuel, beverages, furniture, decorative items, cosmetics, and more (Rethinam & Krishnakumar, 2022). Because of its wide range of uses, it is famously known as the "Tree of Life." Every part of the coconut tree, from its roots to its leaves, serves as a potential raw material for countless products (Gurbuz & Manaros, 2019). The Philippines produces 15 different coconut-based products, including fresh coconuts, copra, coconut oil, copra cake, desiccated coconut, coconut shells, shell charcoal, shell flour, coconut husks, mattress coir fiber, coir bristles, coir dust and shots, whole nuts, husked coconuts, and coconut water (Moreno et al., 2020).

Mature coconut water is generally treated as waste in the Philippines, with approximately 2.4 billion liters discarded annually, as the focus is primarily on producing copra, coconut oil, and coconut milk, neglecting its potential as a beverage (Aba & Luna, 2024). If not treated, coconut wastewater with high biochemical oxygen demand, high solids, and acidity can rapidly reduce oxygen levels, generate odors and acids, and negatively affect aquatic ecosystems and receiving waters (Kumbar, et al., 2023). Today, industries are increasingly focused on reducing waste generation as part of a preventive management approach to minimized production losses and enhancing environmental sustainability (Rocha et al., 2024).

To address the environmental problems posed by the improper disposal of mature coconut water, it is essential to develop sustainable waste management strategies that promote its utilization in value-added products. Thus, this study aimed to lessen the disposal of mature coconut water by using it as an alternative for distilled water in the preparation of solutions and reagents in soap making process. Furthermore, this study also assesses the soap product made using mature coconut water to ensure the quality and usability of the product.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the usability of soap made in mature coconut water as an alternative for distilled water in reagent preparations for basic soap making process. To utilize the coconut water from mature coconuts, strong base solutions (NaOH, KOH, or Lye) and table salt (NaCl) were dissolved in coconut water to make the solutions for the soap making process. Moisture content analysis, pH values test, and foaming ability test were done to ensure the quality of the soap made in this study.

Thus, in order to demonstrate the soap making process and to test the usability of the soap made, this study answered the following questions:

1. What happens to the reagents (base solutions and salt solutions) prepared after using coconut water instead of distilled water?
2. What happens to the soap product after using the reagents used in the soap making process?
3. Comparing the soap made and the soap sold in the market, what are their significant differences in terms of the following criteria:
 - 3.1 Moisture content
 - 3.2 pH value
 - 3.3 Foaming ability

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed an experimental design to evaluate mature coconut water as an alternative to distilled water in reagent preparation for basic soap production, particularly during the saponification process. It further examined whether the physicochemical properties of mature coconut water can support soap formation without compromising product quality, safety, and cleansing efficiency. A comparative analysis was conducted between soaps produced using distilled water (control) and those prepared with mature coconut water (treatment), focusing on key parameters such as pH, moisture content, and foam height.

Research Procedure

Soap production begins with preparing all required base and supplementary materials. The primary materials and reagents are palm oil, mature coconut water, 99% NaOH, Essential oil as fragrance and pigment for color

To produce the soap product by cold process, the procedures are the following:

The alkali solution was prepared, 73mL of mature coconut water (filtered) is combined with either 27g of Lye (99% NaOH), stirred until fully dissolved, and heated to

90 °C. Next, the soap formulation is initiated by blending the heated Lye solution with palm oil, and stirring continuously until a uniform mixture is achieved. As the Lye reacts with the oils, the mixture thickens and becomes firm and sticky, indicating the formation of soap through saponification. Other additives such as 2mL of essential oil and pigments were then incorporated. The mixture was stirred thoroughly to ensure homogeneity. Finally, a small amount of essential oi was placed into the mold (if no extract is used), after which the soap mixture is poured in. The molded soap is left undisturbed for two days to allow complete hardening.

After two days, the soap product made was assessed by standard quality testing to ensure usability of the soap product made. The following procedures are used to test the soap product:

pH of the Soap. The pH of the soap was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter. Prior to measurement, the pH meter was calibrated with standard buffer solutions (pH 4.00, 7.00, and 10.00) according to the manufacturer's instructions, rinsing the electrode with distilled water between each buffer to avoid contamination. A 10% (w/v) soap solution was prepared by dissolving approximately 1g of the soap sample in 9–10mL of distilled water and stirring until evenly dispersed. The electrode was then rinsed, gently blotted dry, and immersed into the soap solution, ensuring the sensing bulb was fully submerged. The pH value was recorded once the reading stabilized. Measurements were performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy and reliability, with the electrode rinsed thoroughly after each use and properly stored after completion of the analysis.

Moisture Content of the Soap. The moisture content of the soap was determined using the oven-drying method. First, a clean, dry evaporating dish or moisture dish was weighed and its initial weight recorded. Approximately 2–5g of the soap sample was then accurately weighed and placed into the dish. The sample was dried in a hot air oven at 105 °C for about 2–3hours or until a constant weight was achieved. After drying, the dish containing the sample was removed from the oven and placed in a desiccator to cool to room temperature to prevent moisture absorption from the air. Once cooled, the final weight was recorded. The moisture content was calculated as the percentage loss in weight relative to the initial sample weight using the formula:

Moisture Content (%) = [(Initial Weight – Final Weight) / Initial Weight] × 100.
The determination was performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy and reliability of the results.

Foam Height. A 0.5g soap sample was dissolved in 5mL of distilled water and the resulting mixture was transferred into a 10mL graduated cylinder. The cylinder was shaken with five to eight strokes and then allowed to stand undisturbed. Afterward, the height of the foam formed above the liquid surface was measured and recorded.

Statistical Tools

To determine whether there were any significant differences between the samples, the Student's t-test was applied to compare the mean results of the formulated soap and the commercially available soaps.

Scope and Limitations

This study only aimed to develop soap out of coconut water from mature coconuts as alternative for distilled water in reagent preparations. Furthermore, only moisture content, pH value, and foaming ability of the produced soap were assessed. Thus, the following limitations of the study are:

1. Coconut water utilized on this study is collected from Dumaguete City Public Market only.
2. Availability of chemicals in the laboratory since the research were conducted at St. Louis School Don Bosco, Dumaguete City.
3. Other quality tests for soap products like Acid Value, Total Fatty Matter (TFM), Glycerin Content Test, and Unsaponifiable Matter Test were not analyzed on the soap product made on this study.

The researchers only got one brand of soap in the market in order to compare the usability between the soap made and the soap available in the market.

RESULTS

Figure 1. *Physical appearance of the soap produced using mature coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.) water as an alternative for distilled water in the basic soap-making process, showing a firm, uniformly shaped, and well-cured soap bar.*

Table 1. Comparison of the mean pH, moisture content, and foam height between the soap made from mature coconut water and commercial soap, highlighting the significant differences in their physicochemical properties ($p < 0.05$).

Parameter	Made Soap (Mean \pm SD)	Commercial Soap (Mean \pm SD)	Student's t-test (t-value)	Remarks
pH	10.30 \pm 0.06	8.76 \pm 0.01	29.27	Significantly Different
Moisture content (%)	16.02 \pm 0.10	14.07 \pm 0.13	18.68	Significantly Different
Foam Height (cm)	1.57 \pm 0.06	3.57 \pm 0.06	48.61	Significantly Different

DISCUSSION

The soap produced in this study was formulated using mature coconut water in place of distilled water during the preparation of the sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution for saponification.

Development and Physical Characteristics of the Product

Figure 1 shows the actual appearance of the soap produced using mature coconut water as an alternative for distilled water in the reagent preparation. Mature coconut water, which naturally contains sugars, minerals, and electrolytes such as potassium and sodium (Zhang et al., 2024), was utilized to assess its suitability as an alternative solvent in the basic soap-making process. The resulting soap formed a firm, homogeneous bar with a smooth texture and uniform appearance, indicating that coconut water effectively supported the saponification reaction.

Assessment of the Soap Produced against Other Commercialized Soap

Table 1 shows the summary of the results of the mean pH, moisture content, and foam height of the made soap and the commercial soap which reveals notable differences in their physicochemical properties and performance characteristics. The results showed that the soap made had a higher mean pH (10.30 \pm 0.06) compared to the commercial soap (8.76 \pm 0.01). Since soaps are generally alkaline, typically within the pH range of 9–11, both products fall within acceptable limits (Nova et al., 2025). However, the higher alkalinity of the commercial soap suggests stronger cleansing ability and more effective removal of oils and dirt.

On the other hand, the slightly lower pH of the made soap indicates that it may be milder and less likely to cause skin dryness or irritation, making it potentially more suitable for individuals with sensitive skin (Tarun et al., 2014; Imani et al., 2025). In terms of moisture content, the made soap recorded a higher mean value (16.02 \pm 0.10%) than the commercial soap (14.07 \pm 0.13%). Higher moisture content generally results in a softer

soap bar that dissolves more quickly during use, potentially reducing its lifespan (Neisya et al., 2024). It may also affect storage stability if not properly cured or preserved.

Conversely, the lower moisture content observed in the commercial soap suggests a harder, more compact structure, contributing to increased durability, longer shelf life, and slower rate of wear during usage (Sherazi, 2019). This difference may be attributed to industrial processing techniques, extended curing periods, or the inclusion of hardening agents in commercial formulations (Mardawati et al., 2022).

Regarding foam height, which serves as an indicator of lathering ability, the commercial soap produced a higher mean foam height (3.57 ± 0.06 cm) compared to the made soap (1.57 ± 0.06 cm). Greater foam height is often associated with better surfactant activity and is generally preferred by consumers, as foam is commonly perceived as a sign of effective cleaning (Widiani et al., 2024; Nova et al., 2025; Aspadiah et al., 2025). The superior foaming ability of the commercial soap may be due to the presence of synthetic surfactants or foam-enhancing additives (Mortada et al., 2021; Alves et al., 2024). In contrast, the lower foam height of the made soap could be attributed to its natural formulation and higher moisture content. It is important to note, however, that increased foam production does not necessarily equate to improved cleaning efficiency (Asemavi & Edeka, 2021).

The formulated soap and commercial soap showed significant differences in all measured parameters ($p < 0.05$). The commercial soap had a lower mean pH, indicating a milder, skin-friendly formulation, while the soap made was more alkaline and likely more effective at cleansing. The made soap exhibited higher moisture content, resulting in a softer texture, whereas the commercial soap was harder and more durable. In terms of foam height, the commercial soap produced greater lather, though the made soap still demonstrated acceptable foaming performance.

Conclusions

The study demonstrated that mature coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.) water can effectively be used as an alternative for distilled water in the basic soap-making process. The soap formulated using coconut water exhibited a higher pH, lower moisture content, and lower foam height compared to commercial soap, with all differences being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). These results suggest that the made soap has cleansing ability due to high pH, softer, and potentially more suitable for sensitive skin but skin irritability test should also be done, although it produces less foam than commercial alternatives. Overall, the use of coconut water in soap making is feasible and produces a quality product with acceptable physicochemical characteristics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to further improve the quality, safety, and performance of the soap made from mature coconut water:

1. Further studies could explore optimizing the formulation to improve foam height while maintaining the mildness and higher moisture content.
2. Natural additives, such as mild surfactants or essential oils, may be incorporated to enhance lather, fragrance, and consumer appeal.
3. Long-term stability tests are recommended to assess shelf life and storage conditions of the soap made with coconut water.
4. This formulation can be promoted as a natural, skin-friendly alternative to commercial soaps, particularly for individuals with sensitive or dry skin.
5. It is also recommended to conduct additional assessments to fully characterize the quality and performance of the soap made with mature coconut water. Hardness or texture analysis can assess the firmness and durability of the soap bar, while determining total fatty matter (TFM) and free alkali content ensured proper saponification and safety for skin use. Solubility or dissolution rate tests can provide insight into usability and longevity, and stability testing over time can assess shelf-life and storage requirements. Additionally, skin irritation tests or patch tests are advised to confirm the mildness and suitability of the soap for sensitive skin. If intended as an antibacterial product, antimicrobial activity assays against common microorganisms can also be included. Incorporating these tests will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the soap's physicochemical properties, safety, and consumer acceptability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured that the coconut (*Cocos nucifera L.*) samples were sourced from the public market were harvested through sustainable practices that did not harm the ecosystem or threaten the species. Proper disposal of plant residues was strictly observed following the experiment to reduce environmental impact. All chemicals utilized during testing were handled, stored, and disposed of in accordance with applicable local regulations and safety guidelines. Furthermore, the research did not involve the use of animals, thereby eliminating any concerns related to animal welfare.

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